

Supplemental Figure S1

In immature wild type, *Batf3*^{-/-} and *Clec9a*^{gfp/-} mice, whole lung IL-5 mRNA expression is not affected by hyperoxic exposure and/or RV infection. Two day-old wild type C57BL/6J, *Batf3*^{-/-} or *Clec9a*^{gfp/-} mice were exposed to normoxia or hyperoxia for 14 days and subsequently inoculated with sham or RV. Five days after sham or RV infection whole lung IL-5 mRNA expression was analyzed by qPCR. One-way ANOVA was performed and there were no significant differences between any of the treatment groups.